

SI Table 1 - List of packages needed for conducting the statistical root length analysis in Rstudio.

Package	Version	Reference
ARTool	0.11.1	Wobbrock et al. (2011)
car	3.1-2	
carData	3.0-5	
dplyr	1.1.4	Wickham et al. (2023)
emmeans	1.10.1	Lenth (2024)
ggplot2	3.5.1	Wickham (2016)
ggpubr	0.6.0	Kassambara (2023a)
magrittr	2.0.3	Bache and Wickham (2022)
psych	2.4.3	Revelle (2024)
rstatix	0.7.2	Kassambara (2023b)
tidyr	1.3.1	Wickham et al. (2024)

Wickham H (2016): ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis: Springer-Verlag New York. Available online at <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>, [06.05.2024].

Wickham H, Francois R, Henry L, Müller Kl, Vaughan D (2023): dplyr: A Grammar of Data Manipulation. Available online at <https://github.com/tidyverse/dplyr>, [06.05.2024].

Wickham, H; Vaughan, D; Girlich, M (2024): tidyr: Tidy Messy Data. R package version 1.3.1. Available online at <https://tidyr.tidyverse.org>, [06.05.2024].

Wobbrock J O, Findlater L, Gergle D, Higgins J J (2011): The aligned ranktransform for nonparametric factorial analyses using only anova procedures. In: **Desney T, Geraldine F, Carl G, Bo B, Wendy A K** (Eds.): CHI 2011. Conference proceedings and extended abstracts; the 29th Annual CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems; Vancouver, BC, May 7 -12, 2011. CHI '11: CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. Vancouver BC Canada, 07 05 2011 12 05 2011. New York, NY: ACM, pp. 143–146.

Bache S M, Wickham H (2022): magrittr: A Forward-Pipe Operator for R. Available online at <https://magrittr.tidyverse.org> [06.05..2024].

Lenth R V (2024): emmeans: Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means. Available online at <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>. [06.05.2024]

Kassambara A (2023a): ggpubr: 'ggplot2' Based Publication Ready Plots. R package version v0.6.0. Available online at <https://rpkgs.datanovia.com/ggpubr/>, checked on [06.05.2024].

Kassambara A (2023b): rstatix: Pipe-Friendly Framework for Basic Statistical Tests. R package version 0.7.2. Available online at <https://rpkgs.datanovia.com/rstatix/>, [06.05.2024].

Revelle W (2024): psych: Procedures for Psychological, Psychometric, and Personality Research. Available online at <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/psych/psych.pdf>. [06.05.2024]